

CORRELATION BETWEEN THYROID HORMONES, CYTOKINE PROFILE, AND RENAL FUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH GLOMERULONEPHRITIS

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Understanding immunoendocrine mechanisms in glomerulonephritis is essential for improving prognostic assessment and identifying systemic factors influencing disease progression.

Relevance: Understanding immunoendocrine mechanisms in glomerulonephritis is essential for improving prognostic assessment and identifying systemic factors influencing disease progression.

Objective: To evaluate correlation relationships between thyroid hormone levels, cytokine parameters, and indicators of renal function in different clinical variants of glomerulonephritis.

Materials and Methods: A cohort of 103 patients with glomerulonephritis aged 18–60 years was examined. Thyroid hormones (TSH, free T4, free T3), anti-TPO antibodies, and cytokines were assessed using ELISA. Correlation analysis was applied to determine relationships between hormonal, immunological, and renal parameters ($p < 0.05$).

Results: Free T4 and free T3 demonstrated positive correlations with urine specific gravity, diuresis, erythrocyte count, CD25+ lymphocytes, and IFN- γ , and negative correlations with IL-1 β , IL-8, ESR, serum creatinine, urea, and proteinuria ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, TSH and anti-TPO antibodies showed negative correlations with glomerular filtration rate, tubular reabsorption, serum albumin, and urine concentration ability, indicating their adverse impact on renal function.

Conclusions: The identified correlations confirm the pathogenetic significance of thyroid hormones and cytokines in glomerulonephritis and support the role of immunoendocrine imbalance in renal impairment.